

EMPLOYMENT ASSURANCE THROUGH THE "WOMEN'S NOTEBOOK" PROJECT

Husanova Gulsum Baxtiyorovna

Banking and finance academy of Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13938080>

Employment assurance for women is a critical issue in many developing countries, including Uzbekistan. One of the most notable initiatives addressing this challenge is the "Ayollar daftari" (Women's Notebook) project. This project aims to support women by enhancing their access to employment, professional development, and financial assistance. Using the Harvard Negotiation Method, which emphasizes principled negotiation and objective criteria, this article examines the success and challenges of the "Women's Notebook" project in ensuring employment for women.

Problem Identification: Ensuring Employment for Women
The "Women's Notebook" project was created to mitigate unemployment among women, particularly in vulnerable segments of the population. The core issue revolves around how to provide meaningful, sustainable employment to these women, taking into consideration the local economic, cultural, and social factors. Many women face barriers such as a lack of education, social expectations, limited professional networks, and unequal access to resources.

Parties Involved

1. **Government:** The primary initiator of the "Women's Notebook" project. The government is responsible for policy-making, funding, and providing institutional support.
2. **Women Beneficiaries:** The women, particularly from low-income backgrounds, are the primary stakeholders. Their needs include access to jobs, vocational training, and financial assistance.
3. **Local Employers:** Businesses that employ women from the project, playing a critical role in offering job opportunities and career advancement.
4. **Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs):** NGOs provide vocational training, mentorship, and advocacy for women's employment rights.
5. **International Organizations:** These organizations support the initiative through financial assistance, training programs, and expertise.

Interests

1. **Government:** The government seeks to reduce unemployment, increase women's participation in the workforce, and promote economic growth.

2. Women: Women want sustainable jobs that offer fair pay, job security, and opportunities for growth.
3. Employers: Employers need skilled and reliable employees who contribute to productivity.
4. NGOs and International Organizations: Their interest lies in ensuring gender equality, women's empowerment, and the success of community development programs.

Options for Mutual Gain

1. Vocational Training Programs: Offering specialized training for women in growing industries such as IT, healthcare, and small business entrepreneurship.
2. Microfinancing and Business Support: Providing women with access to small loans and resources to start their own businesses.
3. Collaborative Employment Models: Developing partnerships between government, private sector, and NGOs to create job opportunities tailored to women's needs.
4. Mentorship and Networking Initiatives: Encouraging mentorship programs where experienced professionals can guide women in their career paths, increasing their confidence and employability.

The "Women's Notebook" project represents a crucial initiative in addressing female unemployment. By applying the Harvard Method, we can see how various stakeholders' interests align and how the project creates opportunities for mutual gain. The success of the initiative depends on continued support from all parties, transparent communication, and ongoing assessment based on objective criteria.

Through principled negotiation, the "Women's Notebook" project can continue to improve employment prospects for women, ultimately contributing to social and economic development in Uzbekistan.

References:

1. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to further strengthen the guarantees of labor rights of women and support entrepreneurial activity", PQ-4235 dated 07.03.2019
2. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to radically improve activities in the field of support of women and strengthening of the Family Institute", PF-5325 dated 02.02.2018